

Mediating Role of Occupational Stress in the Relationship between Work-family Conflict and Family Adjustment among Female Bank Employees

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The purpose of the study was to examine the potential mediating effects of occupational stress dimensions on the relationship between work-family conflict and family adjustment among female bank employees. Work-family conflict scale (Singh & Singh, 1996), family adjustment inventory (high score denotes maladjustment) for working women (Singh, 1987), and occupational stress index (Srivastava & Singh, 1981) were administered individually to 250 clerical level female bank employees in the age range of 25-50 yrs educated at least up to the level of graduation and employed in nationalized banks in Varanasi and nearby regions in the state of Uttar Pradesh, India. Data analysis using Pearson's r and partial correlations revealed that occupational stress partially mediates the relationship. The analysis further revealed that all dimensions of occupational stress, viz., Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, and Strenuous Working Conditions as well as Overall Occupational Stress, served as partial mediators in the relationship between both Work-to-Family (W-to-F) and Family-to-Work (F-to-W) conflict and Overall Family Adjustment. These findings offer significant theoretical and practical insights into the interplay of work-family conflict, family adjustment, and occupational stress among women employed in the banking sector. The study provided valuable insights into the work-family conflict, family adjustments, and job-related stress factors experienced by working women in the banking sector. Consequently, employers should prioritize creating supportive workplace conditions that minimize negative impacts on family life of working women. Recommended measures include avoiding late working hours, offering flexible schedules, and providing access to psychological counseling for women experiencing adjustment difficulties.

Keywords: Work-family conflict, family maladjustment, occupational stress, female bank employees

Managing two demanding worlds at once—the workplace and the home—presents a special set of challenges for modern working women. In the context of women working in the banking industry, which is particularly demanding due to its high-pressure work culture, strict schedules, and performance expectations, this study investigates how occupational stress mediates the relationship between work-family conflict and family maladjustment.

The stress of juggling the demands of being a wife, mother, homemaker, and worker all at once frequently becomes too much for women to handle. There is little room for flexibility in the banking industry because of the long hours and strict goals. This ongoing conflict between work and home responsibilities causes stress over time, which impairs family functioning and results in maladjustment. The precise mechanisms by which occupational stress converts work-family conflict into family maladjustment are still poorly understood, especially when it comes to Indian female bank employees, despite the increasing amount of research on this topic. The goal of this study is to close this gap in the body of current literature.

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Work-family Conflict

When the demands of work and family responsibilities become incompatible, work-family conflict occurs (Greenhaus & Beutell, 1985). Work interfering with family (W-to-F) and family interfering with work (F-to-W) are both well-known causes of stress, emotional exhaustion, and diminished well-being (Frone, Russell, & Cooper, 1992; Amstad et al., 2011). Beyond just time and energy limitations, recent studies have broadened this understanding to include behavioral, cognitive, and emotional aspects (Carlson, Kacmar, & Williams, 2000; Michel et al., 2011).

Reduced quality of life is the common result of both conflict directions, despite their empirical differences. While caregiving responsibilities at home can hinder professional focus and productivity, extended work hours may prevent a parent from meeting family obligations. Studies consistently demonstrate that these conflicts have a detrimental effect on psychological well-being, organizational commitment, and job satisfaction (Allen et al., 2020; Shockley & Singla, 2011).

It is important to remember that family and work don't always have to clash; in fact, they can complement one another (Frone, 2003; Greenhaus & Powell, 2006). But when people are heavily involved in family responsibilities and lack organizational flexibility, this facilitative dynamic is much less likely (Sumer & Knight, 2001; Kossek & Lautsch, 2012). The risk of negative spillover is disproportionately higher for women, who typically place a higher emotional priority on family responsibilities (Cinamon & Rich, 2002; Lapierre et al., 2018).

Deeply ingrained cultural norms in India that still view

homemaking as women's primary duty increase this risk. Indian women are usually expected to prioritize the home when work and family obligations conflict, which increases role strain and its psychological effects (Pradhan & Pradhan, 2015). Yadav (2019) revealed that among female bank employees, all aspects of occupational stress and family maladjustment were positively correlated with both directions of work-family conflict.

Occupational Stress

When a person's ability to handle the demands of their job is exceeded, occupational stress results (Beehr & Newman, 1978). This difficulty is particularly noticeable for working women, who are particularly burdened with juggling the emotional, mental, and practical obligations of home life in addition to the demands of their professional roles. The most prevalent workplace stressors, according to research, are role ambiguity, excessive workload, poor peer relationships, job insecurity, and inadequate supervisory support (Cartwright & Cooper, 2002; Coetzer & Rothmann, 2007). Recent research suggests that emotional labor and technostress are additional issues in contemporary workplaces (Molino et al., 2020; Nixon et al., 2011).

It is commonly acknowledged that one of the main causes of occupational stress is role stress, which includes role conflict, role ambiguity, and role overload (Kahn et al., 1964; Cooper & Marshall, 1976). When conflicting demands make it impossible to fulfill every role expectation at once, role conflict arises. Uncertainty about the requirements of a role is reflected in role ambiguity. Having more responsibilities than one can reasonably handle is known as role overload. Particularly for women in high-demand occupations, all three are strong indicators of burnout, diminished organizational commitment, and intention to leave (Özbağ & Ceyhan, 2014; Wang et al., 2020).

Yadav (2014) showed that the psychological well-being of female bank employees in India is negatively impacted by work-to-home spillover, interpersonal challenges, professional under enrichment, and low occupational status. It's interesting to note that while moderate levels of stress can spur performance (Scott, 1966) prolonged, unrelieved stress consistently compromises functioning, family life, and health (Nixon et al., 2011; Caesens et al., 2017).

Adjustment

The best way to conceptualize adjustment is as a dynamic, ongoing process in which people modify their behavior to coexist peacefully with their surroundings (Gates & Jersild, 1973). It is a continuous balancing act between individual needs and situational demands rather than a one-time accomplishment. Resilience, adaptability, and the ability to start constructive change are characteristics of a well-adjusted individual (Compas et al., 2017). Maladjustment, which shows up as psychological distress, interpersonal problems, and impaired everyday functioning, occurs when this balance is upset by excessive role demands, scarce resources, or ongoing stress (Lazarus & Folkman, 1984).

Finding this balance is especially difficult for married working women. Time, energy, and emotional resources are frequently exceeded by the concurrent demands of work, marriage, parenting, and household responsibilities (Cinamon & Rich, 2002). According to research, role overload, conflict, and ambiguity are some of the best indicators of maladjustment among working women, which can

have negative effects on family cohesion, parental engagement, and marital satisfaction (Allen et al., 2020; Shockley et al., 2017).

These difficulties are made worse in India by enduring gender disparities in the distribution of domestic labor. Indian women continue to shoulder a disproportionate amount of household and caregiving responsibilities despite increasing professional participation, with little institutional or familial support (Pradhan & Pradhan, 2015). Yadav and Kumar (2020) revealed that younger female bank employees had the highest levels of family maladjustment and household stress, with adjustment gradually improving across life stages. This finding emphasizes the vulnerability of early-career women as well as the gradual adaptation that comes with experience.

The quality of functioning within the family unit, including marital harmony, parent-child relationships, household management, and emotional closeness, is reflected in family adjustment, a particular domain of overall adjustment (Olson, 2000). It is challenging to end a self-reinforcing cycle of stress and conflict when professional demands persistently invade this domain without intentional organizational and individual intervention (Allen et al., 2020; Kossek & Lautsch, 2012).

Women in the Banking Sector

Second only to teaching, banking is one of the most popular occupations for Indian women. Its appeal stems from its well-organized work schedule, fair compensation, and generally secure workplace all of which seem compatible with household duties. But the truth is more nuanced. Many Indian bank branches still rely on over-the-counter operations despite the rise of digital banking, which exposes female employees to the interpersonal stressors of working with customers (Yadav, 2014). The pressure is increased by the daily handling of substantial sums of money. The ten-to-five schedule used by the majority of public sector banks leaves little time for family obligations. Working hours frequently extend during quarterly account-closing periods, particularly in March when children's yearly exams take place. This results in a particularly stressful convergence of professional and parental demands. The psychological and temporal resources required for family life, social interaction, and personal healing are gradually depleted by these demands.

Review of Literature

Work-family conflict has been shown to have negative effects on well-being, marriage happiness, and parental functioning across culture and professions. Aycan and Eskin (2005) discovered that among dual-earner Turkish parents, work-family conflict was negatively correlated with psychological well-being and marital satisfaction while Janzen, Muhajarine, and Kelly (2007) reported comparable results among Canadian police officers. According to Yadav and Kumar (2008), younger women in India had noticeably more work-family conflict than their mid-adult counterparts, therefore highlighting the special vulnerability of early-career working women.

Stressors related to one's job greatly exacerbate these effects. Among managerial women in Sri Lankan banking, Kodagoda (2010) pointed to mothering and job duties as the main causes of work-family stress. Extrinsic work, overcommitment, and work-family conflict were favorably connected with depressive

symptoms among Chinese bank employees, according to Kan and Yu (2016), who also found that psychological capital partially offset these impacts. Liu et al. (2012) and Shen et al. (2014) further demonstrated that occupational stress exerts both direct and indirect effects on psychological outcomes.

The mediating role of stress has been an important focus of recent research. Hauk and Chodkiewicz (2013) identified general stress as a mediator between workaholism and work-family conflict, and Singh and Nayak (2015) found that stress mediated the link between work-family conflict and job satisfaction. Within the Indian banking context, Yadav (2017) established that effort constraint, economic constraint, and overall household constraint partially mediated the relationship between W-to-F conflict and mental health, while only effort and overall household constraint mediated the F-to-W conflict and mental health pathway.

Yadav and Kumar (2017) found that occupational stress correlated negatively with mental health across all life stages, with mental health improving progressively from early to later career stages. Social support moderated these relationships differentially; informational support was significant at Stage-I, while companionship support mattered most at Stage-II. Yadav and Kumar (2015) and Yadav (2015) both reported that female bank employees in early adulthood experienced poorer mental health and greater household stress than teachers, with differences diminishing in mid-adulthood.

It's important to remember that working isn't always bad. Women who had good attitudes about employment saw health benefits from working, according to Repetti, Mathews, and Waldron (1989). This points to the fact that individual assessment and available support have a significant impact on the link between role demands and adjustment, not just role demands alone. That said, when work-family conflict is compounded by occupational stress and inadequate support, the consequences for adjustment are consistently negative (Yadav, 2014; Yadav & Kumar, 2017; Yadav, 2018).

Objectives of the Study

- To study the mediating role of all the dimensions of occupational stress, viz., Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, Strenuous Working Conditions and Overall Occupational Stress in the relationship between Work-to-Family Conflict and Overall Family Maladjustment.
- To study the mediating role of all the dimensions of occupational stress, viz., Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, Strenuous Working Conditions and Overall Occupational Stress in the relationship between Family-to-Work Conflict and Overall Family Maladjustment.

Hypotheses of the Study

- All the dimensions of occupational stress, viz., Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, Strenuous Working Conditions and Overall Occupational Stress will mediate the relationship between Work-to-Family Conflict and Overall Family Maladjustment.
- All the dimensions of occupational stress, viz., Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, Strenuous Working Conditions and Overall Occupational Stress will mediate the relationship between

Family-to-Work Conflict and Overall Family Maladjustment.

Method

Participants

The sample for the present study consisted of 250 female bank employees in the age range of 25-50 yrs educated at least up to the level of graduation and employed in nationalized banks in Varanasi and nearby regions.

Measures

The following instruments were used for assessing the various aspects under study.

Work-Family Conflict Scale (Singh & Singh, 1996): Which consists of 22 items, half for assessing work-to-family and half for assessing family-to-work conflict. Each item has five response alternatives ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. The reliability of the scale is 0.86.

Occupational Stress Index (Srivastava & Singh, 1981): It assesses the extent of stress which employees perceive arising from various constituents and conditions of their job. The scale consists of 46 items, each to be rated on the five-point scale, out of which, 28 are 'true-keyed' and the remaining 18 are 'false-keyed'. In the present study only 26 items were selected from the full scale viz., role overload (RO), role conflict (RC), poor peer relations (PPR), intrinsic impoverishment (II), low status (LS) and strenuous working conditions (SWC).

Family Adjustment Inventory for Working Women (Singh, 1987): It assesses the family adjustment of married working women in context of adjustment within five areas, viz., personal, family, children, husband and elders and relations. It may be pointed out at the outset that high scores on this scale denote maladjustment in the particular area hence, the term 'Maladjustment' has been used instead of 'Adjustment' in the results and other sections which follow. The scale thus gives measures of personal maladjustment (11 Items), family maladjustment (16 Items), maladjustment with children (13 Items), maladjustment with husband (15 Items), maladjustment with elders and relations (11 Items) and overall family maladjustment.

The tests were administered to the subjects individually after explaining the purpose of the study and establishing rapport with them.

Results

The data of the study were analysed using Pearson correlation and Partial correlation analysis. In the present study, work-to-family (W-to-F) and family-to-work (F-to-W) conflict were treated as predictor variables. The criterion variable is maladjustment. The mediator variables are dimensions of occupational stress, i.e., role overload, role conflict, poor peer relations, intrinsic impoverishment, low status, strenuous working conditions and overall occupational stress. Partial correlation analysis was applied to clarify the relationship between Work-Family Conflict and Overall Family Maladjustment, controlling for Dimensions of Occupational Stress. This analysis was carried out to determine Work-Family Conflict and Overall Family Maladjustment could be construed as direct or indirect (i.e., mediated by occupational stress (role overload, role conflict, poor peer relations, intrinsic impoverishment, low status, strenuous working conditions)).

First, of all analyse the bivariate (zero-order) correlations among the variables and get a Pearson correlation matrix with two-tailed p levels, with significant values indicated by asterisks. The bivariate correlation matrix, confirms that correlations between all pairs of variables, were significant at $p < 0.05$ or better. That suggests that it makes sense to proceed with the partial analysis, otherwise not.

Figure 1

Relationship between W-to-F Conflict & Maladjustment Mediated by Role Overload

Figure 2

Relationship between W-to-F Conflict & Maladjustment Mediated by Role Conflict

Figure 3

Relationship between W-to-F Conflict & Maladjustment Mediated by Poor Peer Relation

Figure 4

Relationship between W-to-F Conflict & Maladjustment Mediated by Intrinsic Impoverishment

Figure 5

Relationship between W-to-F Conflict & Maladjustment Mediated by Low Status

Figure 6

Relationship between W-to-F Conflict & Maladjustment Mediated by Strenuous Working Conditions

Figure 7

Relationship between W-to-F Conflict & Maladjustment Mediated by Overall Occupational Stress

Figure 8

Relationship between F-to-W Conflict & Maladjustment Mediated by Role Overload

Figure 9

Relationship between F-to-W Conflict & Maladjustment Mediated by Role Conflict

The result of the partial correlation analysis is shown in Tables-1 and 2. Result Table-1 shows the bivariate correlation between W-to-F conflict and overall family maladjustment was $r(df=247) = 0.513$, $p < 0.01$, two-tailed. As previously noted, higher scores on the adjustment scale are indicative of maladjustment in the respective domain. Accordingly, the findings reveal that women reporting elevated levels of work-to-family (W-to-F) conflict demonstrated significantly greater maladjustment. However, Table-1, Figures 1 to 7 clearly indicates that when Role Overload was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.48$, $p < 0.01$, two-tailed. When Role Conflict was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.45$, $p < 0.01$, two-tailed. When Poor Peer Relation was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.41$, $p < 0.01$, two-tailed. When Intrinsic Impoverishment was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.39$, $p < 0.01$, two-tailed. When Low Status was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.46$, $p < 0.01$, two-tailed. When Strenuous

Working Conditions were controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.41, p < 0.01$, two-tailed. And when Overall Occupational Stress was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.30, p < 0.01$, two-tailed. Therefore, it can be inferred that the relationship between W-to-F conflict and overall family maladjustment is partly mediated by role overload, role conflict, poor peer relations, intrinsic impoverishment, low status, strenuous working conditions and Overall Occupational Stress.

Figure 10

Relationship between F-to-W Conflict & Maladjustment Mediated by Poor Peer Relation

Figure 11

Relationship between F-to-W Conflict & Maladjustment Mediated by Intrinsic Impoverishment

Figure 12

Relationship between F-to-W Conflict & Maladjustment Mediated by Low Status

Figure 13

Relationship between F-to-W Conflict & Adjustment Mediated by Strenuous Working Conditions

Figure 14

Relationship between F-to-W Conflict & Adjustment Mediated by Overall Occupational Stress

Table 1

Mediating Effect of Dimensions of Occupational Stress (M.V.) on the Relationship between Work-to-Family Conflict (P.V.) and Overall Family Maladjustment (C.V.)

	Role Overload	Role Conflict	Poor Peer Relation	Intrinsic Impoverishment	Low Status	Strenuous Working Conditions	Overall Occupational Stress
Pr. V. / Med. V	.374**	.364**	.372**	.431**	.253**	.368**	.554**
Cr. V. / Med. V	.204**	.292**	.451**	.447**	.445**	.445**	.536**
Pr. V. / Cr. V	.513**	.513**	.513**	.513**	.513**	.513**	.513**
Pr. V. / Cr. V (Controlling for M. V.)	.481**	.456**	.417**	.397**	.462**	.419**	.307**
Mediation Conditions Satisfied	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Table 2

Mediating Effect of Dimensions of Occupational Stress (M.V.) on the Relationship between Family-to-Work Conflict (P.V.) and Overall Family Maladjustment (C.V.)

	Role Overload	Role Conflict	Poor Peer Relation	Intrinsic Impoverishment	Low Status	Strenuous Working Conditions	Overall Occupational Stress
Pr. V. / Med. V	.456**	.412**	.315**	.372**	.258**	.356**	.572**
Cr. V. / Med. V	.204**	.292**	.451**	.447**	.445**	.445**	.536**
Pr. V. / Cr. V	.454**	.454**	.454**	.454**	.454**	.454**	.454**
Pr. V. / Cr. V (Controlling for M. V.)	.415**	.383**	.369**	.347**	.392**	.354**	.213**
Mediation Conditions Satisfied	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES

Table-2 shows the bivariate correlation between F-to-W conflict and overall maladjustment was $r(df=247) = 0.454, p < 0.01$, two-tailed. This indicates that women with high F-to-W conflict had

significantly greater maladjustment. However, Table-2, Figure 8 to 14 clearly indicates that when Role Overload was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.41, p < 0.01$, two-tailed.

When Role Conflict was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.38, p < 0.01$, two-tailed. When Poor Peer Relation was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.36, p < 0.01$, two-tailed. When Intrinsic Impoverishment was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.34, p < 0.01$, two-tailed. When Low Status was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.39, p < 0.01$, two-tailed. When Strenuous Working Condition was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.35, p < 0.01$, two-tailed. And when Overall Occupational Stress was controlled, the correlation value dropped to $r(df=247) = 0.21, p < 0.01$, two-tailed. Therefore, it can be inferred that role overload, role conflict, poor peer relations, intrinsic impoverishment, low status, strenuous working conditions and Overall Occupational Stress partly mediate the relationship between F-to-W conflict and overall family maladjustment.

Discussion

The role of women in India has changed drastically attaining a new definition and perspective in the last few decades. The teaching jobs, traditionally preferred by women, are gradually being replaced by search for job openings in more competitive and demanding fields, and banking sector has emerged as one of the most common choices. A job in bank entails high level of responsibility and, hence, can be more demanding and also associated with high levels of stresses and work-family conflict. A women employed in bank, despite a high salary, is required to remain at job the whole day and on days of financial closing or any other contingency this may get extended. For women who have young children, or small babies, this could lead to serious conflict between serving the interests of the job as well as the home.

This study, therefore, aimed at examining the mediating role of Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, Strenuous Working Conditions and Overall Occupational Stress in the relationship between Work-Family Conflict and overall family maladjustment.

Results revealed that women with high W-to-F conflict had higher overall family maladjustment. However, it can infer that the relationship between W-to-F conflict and overall family maladjustment is partially mediated by Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, Strenuous Working Conditions and Overall Occupational Stress. *The first hypothesis H1 which posits "Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, Strenuous Working Conditions and Overall Occupational Stress will mediate the relationship between Work-to-Family Conflict and Overall Family Maladjustment", has been partially supported in context to Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, Strenuous Working Conditions and Overall Occupational Stress.*

Correlation between F-to-W conflict and overall family maladjustment indicates that women with high F-to-W conflict had higher overall family maladjustment and the relationship between F-to-W conflict and overall family maladjustment is partially mediated by Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, Strenuous Working Conditions and Overall Occupational Stress. *Thus, the second hypothesis H2 which posits "Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, Strenuous Working Conditions and*

Overall Occupational Stress will mediate the relationship between Family-to-Work Conflict and Overall Family Maladjustment", has been partially supported in context to Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, Strenuous Working Conditions and Overall Occupational Stress.

The results demonstrate that Role Overload partially mediates the relationship between both Work-to-Family (W-to-F) and Family-to-Work (F-to-W) conflict and Overall Family Maladjustment. Emerging as a crucial intermediate mechanism is Role Overload, conceptually defined as a state in which an individual perceives insufficient time to complete all required responsibilities and experiences the total expectations of significant roles as beyond their capacity for effective performance. Given the double burden of professional and family duties, within the purview of this study, women working in the banking industry seem especially prone to role overload. This inability to properly balance competing role demands therefore worsens work-family conflict, which contributes to higher Overall Family Maladjustment.

Role conflict is a conflict among the roles corresponding to two or more statuses. A person occupies various roles as a member of the organization, society, family etc. when their different roles make conflicting demands on the person and make it difficult for him to fulfil these demands, then it leads to feeling of stress due to role conflict. Poor peer relations refer to inability to maintain adequate social relations with a social group consisting of people who are equal in such respects as age, education, or social class. Intrinsic impoverishment refers to a feeling that being in the work role is not leading the person towards fulfilment of desired goals nor is enhancing the ability or skill of the concerned individual. Low status refers when an individual feels that the position he/she is occupying is a position of inferior status stress occurs. Conditions which strain the system by demanding more than the physical capacities of the individual lead to stress due to strenuous working conditions.

So finally, it may be concluded that the mediating variables Role Overload, Role Conflict, Poor Peer Relations, Intrinsic Impoverishment, Low Status, Strenuous Working Conditions and Overall Occupational Stress "partly explains" the correlation between Work-Family Conflict and Overall Family Maladjustment. Therefore, obtained results of the study partially confirmed the hypothesis. So, in conclusion we can say that work-family conflict alone may not lead to poor family adjustment but occupational stress emanating from the conflict may be the reason for the negative family adjustment consequences. Thus, the results convey that the occupational stress exerts a profound and consequential influence on the family adjustment of working women - an effect that is amplified among those simultaneously pursuing professional achievement and fulfilling familial obligations. The study emphasizes the crucial necessity of organized support systems meant for working women at both the organizational and family levels. Employers, especially those hiring younger women, are encouraged to take proactive steps to put welfare-oriented policies in place, such as remote work opportunities, childcare services integrated into the workplace, subsidized housing, and psychosocial support programs. The role of the family unit itself is equally important. A strong protective factor can be an atmosphere of acceptance, emotional support, and fair distribution of household chores among family members, therefore improving the family adaptation of working women and enabling them to reach their full potential in both personal and professional spheres.

Implications and Suggestions

The current study offers important theoretical and practical insights into the dynamics of occupational stress, work-family conflict and family adjustment among women working in the banking industry. The results call for immediate and ongoing institutional attention since they have significant ramifications for organizational policy, human resource management, and employee well-being.

Banks and financial organizations at the organizational level have to realize their critical responsibility in building a welcoming and inclusive workplace for female staff members. An important step in this path is to improve the social support framework inside banking institutions. This can be accomplished by organised training courses for Heads of Operations, Business Development Managers, and other supervisory staff, providing them with skills in proactive supervision, conflict resolution, stress management, and team cohesiveness. Regular staff retreats and peer support forums could also help to foster a sense of teamwork and organizational belonging among female employees.

Beyond traditional approaches, banks are strongly urged to investigate and institutionalise evidence-based wellness methods including progressive muscle relaxation training, mindfulness-based meditation programmes, professional psychological counselling, and crisis intervention training. These steps are not only restorative but also proactive investments in maintaining a psychologically robust and economically successful workforce. Moreover, setting up Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs) geared particularly to the needs of working women might offer a methodical and private outlet for handling adjustment-related challenges before they turn into ongoing stressors.

It is equally important for organizational leaders to understand the larger social cost of ignoring these problems. Neglecting work-family disputes and job-related stress among female banking professionals for an extended period of time lowers personal well-being and organizational productivity and jeopardizes the industry's ability to attract, retain, and promote high-caliber women talent.

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